
THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN MODERN SOCIETY

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Abstract: The article faces reflection on identity of women as well as philosophical principle. Moreover, it depicts the role of the woman in modern society concerning in the vigorous growth of education system.

Keywords: women's education, female, time, modern society, women involvement

Future revolution that will happen in some decades is profoundly depends on education of younger generation. Nowadays in the century of technology, progress, discoveries, emancipation and feminism, this issue is most acute. For many centuries, a woman has been the keeper of the hearth, while everything that had to do with the outside world was taken over by a man. People are used to treat men only as a genius one however it is time to draw an attention to role of women in development of science. A woman in modern society has a completely different status and vocation, she has other values and needs that make us reconsider our views on the female role in today's world. One of the crucial reasons for the change in the female involvement in modern society is the change in attitudes towards women's education and the subsequent increase in the number of educated women. For example, now the education of women in institutes, universities and academies has become commonplace, however, for this, women's education had to overcome a huge path full of various problems and difficulties.

On the territory of Uzbekistan, from 1920 to 1925, the state set its task: to organize and strengthen a new school, to involve as many children of working people as possible in it, to introduce new ideological content everywhere in the school, to train new cadres of teachers. These are the main milestones in the development of women's education, which led to the strengthening of the role of women in society, the growth of their independence and influence. Abdukodir Shakuri was one of the first to advocate the introduction of equal education for girls, and for the first time carried out joint education of boys and girls in his school. With the establishment of Independence, the education system was reformed. All types of education have become available to women. Equality has been established between women and men.

Currently, many girls are studying in higher educational institutions, and it is absolutely normal for them to receive specialties that were previously considered male. Time has proved that a woman can do great things with men on equal terms, and sometimes even better than them. Over the years of independent development, our country has achieved great success in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of women. No less significant are the achievements in ensuring their active participation in the socio-political and socio-economic life of the public addition, Uzbekistan was one of the first in Central Asia to ratify the International Labour Organization conventions, such as "On the Elimination of all forms of discrimination against women", "On Maternity Protection", "On discrimination in employment and occupation" and other documents. As an example, we can cite the establishment of a public organization – the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, which has become a productive mechanism for supporting this part of the population, protecting their rights and legitimate interests. Women's participation in public administration is becoming increasingly active. In particular, today they make up 17% of the members of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis and 16% of the deputies of the Legislative Chamber. At the same time, in recent years, the representation of women in executive bodies has increased almost 5 times – from 3.4% to 16%. The number of representatives of the fair sex in the country's political parties has increased by creating a women's wing. Currently, according to the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, the proportion of women in the Liberal Democratic Party of Uzbekistan has increased from 35% to 38%, the Democratic Party "Milliy Tiklanish" - from 40% to 46%, the People's Democratic Party – from 41% to 56%, the Social Democratic Party "Adolat" – from 38% to 49%. Women's participation in local self-government bodies and mahalla structures has also been expanded. So, over the last period, their share of the total number of chairmen of mahalla committees has increased from 9.6% to 25.6%. At the same time, the role of women in the socio-economic life of the country is also expanding. For example, in recent years, the share of the beautiful half of our society in the employment structure has increased from 44 to 45.7%. The number of women entrepreneurs who open their own business and achieve significant success is growing. According to the latest data, the heads of 40.4% of small enterprises and 13.7% of microenterprises are representatives of the fair sex.

It is difficult to imagine the science of Uzbekistan without women today. About ten thousand women scientists are developing new methods of diagnosis and treatment, pedagogical approaches to the upbringing of the younger generation. The number of women scientists working in the field of physics, chemistry and even mechanical engineering is growing from year to year. Non-profit non-governmental and public organizations implementing educational programs play an important role in improving the qualifications of women. For example, various clubs, associations

and centers are successfully working in this direction under the Women's Committee. In particular, the club of women managers promotes the fullest disclosure of leadership qualities and practical capabilities of women, increasing their experience of working with personnel. The Club of Gifted Girls, which unites 700 talented girls, annually holds republican forums where participants demonstrate and discuss their achievements. Centers for social adaptation of women provide psychological, legal support, training. The Program of pedagogical grants established by the Forum of Culture and Art of Uzbekistan Foundation and the Women's Assembly Association plays an important role in the public life of the country. The competition of the Program, held since 2006, promotes the identification of initiative and dedicated teachers, popularization of their working methods and further improvement of professional skills. Teachers working in all levels of the education system can participate in the competition with their projects on new pedagogical technologies and other areas.

Guided by the words of Saida Mirziyoyeva "We are here to learn from each other, to empower and inspire each other, to learn to strengthen the role of women in our societies so that they can make their contribution to the development of human civilization. I believe that Uzbek women have something to say to the world, they will be able to make a significant contribution to the economic and cultural development of the human race".

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